

The experimental site was a lowland ricefield with irrigation facilities in Nirdeshkhali in the coastal area of West Bengal. The soil belonged to mixed, hyperthermic acidic family of Typic Haplaquept. Important characteristics were pH (1:2 water) 3.3, 1.95% organic C, 63% clay (illite dominant), CEC 28.9 meq/100 g, 0.123% total N, 9.8 mg available P/kg, exchangeable K 2.12 meq/100 g, and exchangeable Al 0.911 meq/100 g. Lime required to raise soil pH to 5.5 was 33.21 t CaCO₃/ha.

The experiment was laid out in 20- m² plots, in a randomized block design with four replications. The field was plowed thoroughly, and required lime (CaCO₃) applied before the field was puddled. At harvest, grain yield was sampled and uptake of N, P, K, Fe, and Al determined.

Grain yield of rice MW10 was highest when lime corresponding to 10 times the amount of exchangeable Al (9.11 t CaCO₃/ha) was applied. That amount increased soil pH and counter-

acted the ill effects of Fe and Al. Nutrient uptake by grain was also highest at that lime level (see table). The results indicate that yield was maximized with lime equivalent to or less than the amounts theoretically needed to neutralize toxic quantities of Fe and Al and supply adequate Ca.

Exchangeable Al served as a good estimator of lime required for economic productivity of rice in this acid sulfate soil. ■

Soil microbiology

Response of *Azolla pinnata* to herbicide and time of inoculation

G. Srinivasan, S. Ranganayaki, and P. Pothiraj, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, India

We evaluated the response of azolla to rice herbicides—anilofos alone and in combination with 2,4-D EE (ethyl ester) and thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE—in terms of fresh biomass (FB), relative growth rate (RGR), and chlorophyll content 20 d after herbicide application. Azolla was inoculated 0, 3, and 6 d after herbicide application.

Untreated control recorded the highest FB (see table), but FB with anilofos alone and in combination with 2,4-D EE were comparable. FB was significantly reduced with thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE.

Effects of herbicides and time of azolla inoculation on fresh biomass, RGR, and chlorophyll content of *Azolla pinnata*.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Fresh biomass (t/ha)	RGR (g/g per d)	Chlorophyll (mg/g)	
			'a'	'b'
Herbicides				
Thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE (1.00 + 0.51 kg/ha)	11.22 c	0.20 b	2.30 a	1.39 a
Anilofos + 2,4-D EE (0.30 + 0.51 kg/ha)	17.14 ab	0.22 a	2.29 a	1.40 a
Anilofos (0.40 kg/ha)	15.70 b	0.22 a	2.26 a	1.40 a
Control	17.62 a	0.22 a	2.30 a	1.40 a
Time of azolla inoculation (d after herbicide application)				
On the day	0.61 c	0.06 c	2.32 a	1.42 a
3d day	16.33 b	0.22 b	2.35 a	1.44 a
6th day	23.91 a	0.24 a	2.41 a	1.47 a

^aIn a column within a factor, any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other by LSD (P = 0.05).

Irrespective of herbicide, inoculation of azolla 6 d after herbicide application had the highest FB.

The highest RGR (0.22 g/g per d) was in untreated control and in treatments

with anilofos. Azolla inoculation 6 d after herbicide application had the highest RGR.

Herbicides and times of inoculation had no effect on chlorophyll content. ■

Vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizae (VAM) colonization in lowland rice roots and its effect on growth and yield

P. Sivaprasad, K. K. Sulochana, and M. A. Salam, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Trivandrum 695522, India

VAM association is less frequent in submerged environments than in uplands. To study the colonization pattern of VAM and its effect on lowland rice growth and yield, we raised mycor-

rhizal seedlings in concrete pots (75 × 75 × 2.5 cm) filled with clay loam soil and pre-inoculated with the VAM fungus *Glomus fusciculatum* (3000 spores/0.25 m²). Dry nursery method was followed to facilitate VAM infection. Control seedlings were raised without VAM inoculation. Percent mycorrhizal colonization was recorded 21 d after.

Three sets of 20 seedlings each of mycorrhizal-infected plants and control were transplanted under flooded condition for observation of VAM 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DT).

Crop response with and without NPK was tested in pots using inoculated and

uninoculated seedlings. The six treatments were laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications.

Inoculated seedlings recorded 16.2% VAM infection 21 d after inoculation. Infection persisted and further increased after transplanting. Infection was 20.8% at 15 DT, 28% at 30 DT, and 46% at 45 DT, indicating that flooding did not affect colonization. Control seedlings were also positive for infection at 21 DT because of native VAM. Infection was 8.6% at 30 DT and 14.2% at 45 DT.

Seedling growth and yield with and without NPK application were measured

Effect of VAM inoculation on growth and yield of lowland rice.

Treatment ^a	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Mycorrhizal infection at harvest (%)	Grain yield (g/pot ^b)	Straw (g/pot ^b)
No NPK, no M	88	9	16.1	66.9	55.90
No NPK, with M	103	9	49.3	87.6	72.93
				(31)	(30)
With NK, no M	103.5	10	13.6	83.5	68.25
With NK, with M	104.5	12	50.0	103.5	79.75
				(24)	(17)
With NPK, no M	103	10	12.8	85.2	63.00
With NPK, with M	104	11	43.0	106.2	75.50
				(25)	(20)
LSD (P = 0.05)	ns	ns	23.6	18.1	15.3

^a M = inoculated with *G. fasciculatum*. ^b Figures in parentheses are percent increase over control.

in a separate experiment. Inoculation with *G. fasciculatum* raised mycorrhizal colonization (see table), but its effect on plant height and productive tillers was not significant. Grain and straw yield

increased significantly with VAM inoculation. Facilitating VAM infection by nursery inoculation, following the dry nursery method, can be used to achieve VAM benefits in lowland rice. ■

Effect of planting method and optimum seeding rate on biomass production and nitrogen fixation in *Sesbania rostrata*

A. Tirol-Padre and J. K. Ladha, Soil Microbiology Division, IRRI

We experimented with *S. rostrata* at IRRI Nov 1987-Jan 1988 to determine 1) optimum sampling size for measuring plant density, biomass, and acetylene-reducing activity (ARA), and 2) optimum seeding rate and planting method for higher biomass and N₂ fixation.

Seeding rates were 20, 40, and 60 kg/ha and planting methods were broadcast, row seeding with 15 cm between rows, and row seeding with 30 cm between rows. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Plot size was 2 × 6 m. Biomass and ARA were measured 41 d after seeding (DAS).

For estimating plant density, the 30- × 30-cm sampling unit gave better precision than 30- × 60-cm or 60- × 60-cm for the same sampling area in all treatments. Efficiency appears higher with small samples taken many times rather than big samples taken a few times. Small sampling units are especially recommended for plots with uneven plant distribution. With the 30- × 30-cm sampling unit, the coefficients of vari-

ation (CV) of the mean (\bar{x}) for 4, 8, and 12 samples/block were 12.4, 8.8, and 7.2%, respectively.

For determining plant biomass, the two-plant sampling unit generally gave better precision than the four-plant unit when seed was broadcast or planted in rows. CV (\bar{x}) for 2, 4, and 6 samples/block were 14.6, 10.3, and 8.4%, respectively.

For ARA measurements, the 4-plant sampling unit generally gave better precision when seed was planted in rows (15-30 cm apart) and plant samples were taken from adjacent rows. CV (\bar{x}) for 2, 4, and 6 samples/block were 13.6, 9.6, and 7.9%, respectively. When plants were sampled from the same row or when seeds were broadcast, however, the two-plant sampling unit gave higher precision.

Effect of seeding rate and planting method on a) plant density of *S. rostrata*, b) biomass per unit area of *S. rostrata*. IRRI, 1988.

Row seeding generally resulted in higher germination rate than broadcast seeding, with more plants/m² and biomass/m² at 20 and 40 kg seed/ha. However, row seeding with 30 cm between rows had germination similar to broadcast seeding at 60 kg seed/ha.

When seed was broadcast or sown in rows with 15-cm spacing, increasing the seeding rate from 20 to 60 kg/ha increased the number of plants and plant biomass/m². But with 30 cm between rows, higher seeding rate increased the two parameters only up to 40 kg/ha (see figure); overcrowding within rows resulted in lower germination. Increasing the number of rows (i.e., decreasing the distance between rows to 15 cm) minimized crowding of seeds within rows. This explains why, at 60 kg seed/ha, plant density and biomass/m² were higher with 15 cm than with 30 cm between rows.

Planting method significantly affected ARA/plant, but seeding rate had no effect. Averages of ARA at three seeding rates were 12.1, 10.3, and 9.7 μmol C₂H₄/plant per h for broadcast, 15-cm row seeding, and 30-cm row seeding, respectively, with a standard error of the mean of 0.6. This seems to be related to the lower plant density, when seed was broadcast.

Planting method and seeding rate produced significant effects on ARA per unit area and on biomass per unit area. Estimated ARA per m² was 597, 823, and 746 μmol C₂H₄/plant per h for broadcasting, 15-cm seeding, and 30-cm seeding treatments, respectively, with a standard error of 50. ■